

Global and Indian perspectives of alumina-spinel lining concepts in a steel ladle

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Abstract

Developments in high quality steel production e.g. for automotive applications require adjustments of the steel ladle lining. Apart from lining life and direct refractory cost, other aspects such as ladle capacity, impact on steel quality, and energy saving have gained importance in the "Total cost of ownership" approaches. The paper describes the development of alumina-spinel lining concepts and discusses specific advantages in a modern steel ladle lining. Recent developments around the availability of magnesia and its pricing from China, have triggered other considerations and projects to investigate the replacement of magnesia-carbon by alumina-spinel materials in a steel ladle lining.

1. Introduction

Developments in steel technology over the past 50 years have led to substantial weight reduction in combination with improved strength properties as shown in **fig. 1**. Ultra-low carbon (ULC) and high strength low alloy (HSLA) steel grades have been developed for automotive use. These require advanced processing during secondary metallurgy in the steel ladle ²⁾. 30 to 40 % of production from leading West European flat steel producers is automotive high quality steel.

Fig. 1 Steel development for packaging and automotive ¹⁾.

Indian steel production is continuously growing and reached 106.5 million tonnes in 2018. About 50 % of it is flat steel, but only 7 to 10 % is automotive high quality steel. About 45 % of such steel in India is produced by Tata Steel. The Indian auto industry

is growing at above 10 % CAGR with international companies also establishing production in India. Consequently Indian steel companies have started to look at global end user markets and adapting trends from other regions.

The refractory lining of the steel ladle also contributes to achieving the desired steel quality ²⁾ and alumina-spinel materials provide advantages for high quality steel production. The development of such ladle linings, and some key aspects of that development, will be discussed in this paper.

2. Requirements for steel ladle lining

The refractory lining in steel ladles must fulfil various requirements as shown in **fig. 2**. This compares the relative importance of different factors between the 1990s and 2010s. Safety was always the ultimate pre-requisite and therefore has not been mentioned here. Ladle capacity and steel quality have gained importance over the past 25 years, and there is also a greater focus on energy saving. Simple refractory cost and lining life are no longer the main considerations. Other factors are now involved making it a more complex problem.

Fig. 2 Requirements for steel ladle lining - 1990s and 2010s; safety was a pre-requisite at all times.

3. Alumina-spinel ladle lining

In the 1990s spinel ($MgAl_2O_4$) was introduced to alumina pre-cast shapes such as purging plugs, well blocks and impact pads, and has become the global industry standard. Alumina-rich spinels such as AR

78 and AR 90 were developed ³⁾ and boosted the performance of alumina castables in hot strength, wear- and thermal shock resistance. Alumina-spinel castables for the steel ladle side wall and bottom were first introduced in Japan in the 1990s. A monolithic lining, apart from the MgO/C slag line, has become the industry standard in Japan since then. Alumina-magnesia spinel-forming castables followed and they provide advantages especially in the ladle side wall ^{4,5)}. In Europe and North America, bauxite based castables or alumina-magnesia spinel-forming castables were initially used for monolithic ladle lining ⁶⁾. Later, tabular alumina replaced bauxite, and both concepts - spinel-forming and spinel containing are used today ⁴⁾. About 20 % of steel ladles in Europe contain a monolithic lining, but more often it is just the ladle bottom.

Fig. 3 Pre-heater for monolithic ladles ⁹⁾.

Monolithic steel ladle lining with relining technology provides many advantages e.g. automation and reduced manpower of up to 70 %, faster installation, long lining life (e.g. 114 heats with only 110-136 mm new wall thickness ⁷⁾ and low specific refractory consumption of 0.6 to 0.8 kg/t of steel for side wall and bottom except slag line ^{7,8)}). However, there are several hurdles to be overcome with the change from bricked to monolithic ladles. It requires investment in equipment - a mould, a mixer, and suitable ladle pre-heaters (**fig. 3**). Laser scan supported wear control is also very helpful especially with relining technologies. Modern laser equipment provides wear data and 3D images in a very short time. In 1985 the first generation laser equipment required 60 minutes to measure 500 data points. Modern fourth generation equipment measures three million points in two minutes ¹⁰⁾. Old, deformed ladle shells are not suitable when doing the installation with a mould, because the lining thickness would become

too uneven. Last but not least, training and experience of the operators on the shop floor is important. Projects to introduce monolithic ladle lining in the past have proved that clear management commitment is mandatory in order to make it a successful technology change. Half-hearted approaches have failed. Once successfully implemented, steel works never revert back to bricked ladle linings.

Fired alumina-spinel bricks used to be only a niche product in steel applications. This all changed in 2000 when Corus, now Tata Steel Europe, in IJmuiden/The Netherlands, introduced such bricks to replace andalusite in the steel ladle ¹¹⁾. The new development was triggered by metallurgical requirements and new challenges resulting from the introduction of thin-slab casting. More aggressive slag composition required a more resistant material than andalusite and a carbon-free lining for the side wall (except the slag line) was required in order to reduce carbon pick-up during production of ULC steel. Low silica content in the bricks was found to be essential for good performance ¹¹⁾. The more expensive alumina-spinel bricks solved the technical challenges, but also proved to be economically favourable due to low wear rate, which enabled thinner lining thickness and long lining life (e.g. 140 mm bricks achieve 140 heats). Therefore specific refractory costs were even lower when compared to andalusite bricks ¹²⁾.

In recent years, fired alumina-spinel bricks have also been introduced successfully in Indian steel works, replacing MgO/C bricks - except in the slag line ¹³⁾. Tata Steel Jamshedpur LD 2 steel works is producing Al-killed for flat products in 160 tonnes steel ladles. 60% of production is treated in ladle furnace and 22% in RH-degassing. The average tapping temperature from BOF is 1650°C and average holding time in the steel ladle is between 80 and 100 minutes. C/A+S of the slag is around 1.4. The slag line is MgO/C bricks and the bottom Alu-Mag-Carbon bricks. **Table 1** shows the comparison between MgO/C bricks (2015-2016) and fired alumina-spinel bricks (since 2017) in the metal zone of the ladle. The metal zone lining life was 110 to 160 heats for MgO/C (avg. 133 heats) vs. 120 to 170 heats for fired alumina-spinel (avg. 136 heats), indicating that the metal zone is not the limiting factor for the ladle campaign in most cases. The alumina-spinel bricks provide advantages in more consistent and lower average wear rate (**fig. 4**), reduction of outside steel shell temperature from 295 to 270°C, and 15% cost reduction for the metal zone working lining in the ladle.

Metallurgical requirements for producing high quality automotive steel are becoming more

important in India and will further support this lining concept.

Table 1 Tata Steel Jamshedpur LD 2 steel ladle metal zone lining

Metal zone bricks	MgO/C	Fired Al-Sp
Original thickness [mm]	150	150
Range of lining life [heats]	110-160	120-170
Average lining life [heats]	133	136
Avg. left over thickness [mm]	58	62
Avg. wear rate [mm/heat]	0.69	0.65
Potential of metal zone life at 50 mm residual thickness [heats]	145	154
Steel shell temperature [°C]	295	270
Cost of metal zone lining [%]	100	85

Fig. 4 Wear rate of metal zone bricks Tata Jamshedpur LD 2.

4. Total cost of ownership aspects

4.1 Ladle capacity increase

The steel ladle capacity is often the limiting factor for increasing productivity in a steel plant as it defines the batch size in the processing. Increasing the ladle capacity was therefore a big focus and figure 5 shows how typical lining thickness for wear and safety lining has developed in Europe during the past 25 years. If the additionally produced steel can be sold profitably, increasing the ladle capacity has a tremendous impact on the economic performance of the steel plant ¹⁴⁾. The performance of alumina-spinel linings enables the lowest wear lining thickness and this became a driving factor for these linings e.g. at voestalpine Stahl Linz/Austria ⁷⁾ or Tata Steel Europe Ijmuiden/The Netherlands ¹²⁾.

Fig. 5 Typical refractory lining thickness in steel ladles 1990s – 2010s.

4.2 Energy saving

During treatment and transport of steel in the ladle, it is cooling by typically around 1 K per minute. Heat losses can be reduced by covering the ladle, but this often cannot be done in steelworks. The refractory lining is contributing to temperature losses in two ways. Firstly, there is heat transfer through the lining to the steel shell, which can be reduced e.g. by better insulation or lower thermal conductivity materials in the wear lining. This heat transfer achieves a kind of steady state situation once the lining is completely warmed up, typically after the first 3-4 heats. Secondly, heat loss comes from the thermal cycling of the ladle, where the hot face is cooling down from about 1550 to about 800 °C while the ladle is empty. How much heat gets lost during this empty period depends on the heat capacity and the thermal conductivity of the wear lining (table 2).

Table 2 Graphite content in ladle refractories

	MgO/C bricks	Alumina-spinel	
		Fired bricks	Castables
C [wt%]	5 - 10	-	-
Thermal conductivity [W/mK]	8 - 10	3.5	3.5
Bulk density [g/cm ³]	2.9	3.0 – 3.2	2.9 – 3.0

Fig. 6 compares the temperature loss in a 180 tonnes steel ladle with spinel forming castable to one with MgO/C bricks in the ladle side wall. Because of the higher thermal conductivity of MgO/C (table 2) the temperature loss is 10-15 K higher despite an additional insulation layer in the permanent lining. Taking into account that 1 K temperature loss costs between 5 and 10 € cent per tonne of steel ^{15,16)}, a 15 K higher temperature loss costs 0.75 to 1.5 € per tonne of steel. In general, ladle refractory cost – without the sliding gate system – are in the range of 1.5 to 2 € per tonne of steel. So the cost of heat loss can be more than 50 % of the total ladle refractory cost!

Fig. 6 Cooling of steel in the ladle over 60 minutes without treatment – MgO/C vs. alumina-spinel castable ⁷⁾.

5. Market developments

The alumina-spinel ladle lining concepts discussed in this paper are based on synthetic alumina raw materials, which use alumina from the Bayer process as feedstock. The bauxite ore used for this Bayer process is different from refractory grade bauxite. It has much lower alumina content and is referred to as metallurgical grade bauxite because the major share of synthetic alumina from the Bayer process goes into aluminium production. Only a small percentage is the basis for further value added synthetic alumina raw materials for use in refractories and other advanced applications. China is dominating the global market for supply of refractory grade bauxite, which is 2 to 3 million tonnes per year. This is a small volume when compared to the global market for metallurgical grade bauxite, which, in 2016, globally, was about 262 million tonnes. Interestingly, China accounts for only 3 % of the global bauxite reserves ¹⁷⁾ and imports millions of tonnes of metallurgical bauxite each year to meet the needs of their alumina refineries and aluminium production. The main bauxite resources are located in Guinea, Australia, and Brazil ¹⁷⁾. Therefore for synthetic alumina production, bauxite sourcing is independent from China.

Magnesia based refractories are also often used as steel ladle lining, and China is an important source for the raw material. Changes in Chinese policies led to availability issues and price increases in 2017-2018¹⁸⁾. As described above, synthetic alumina based steel ladle lining concepts are a strategic option in order to reduce dependency upon the Chinese magnesia materials used in MgO/C bricks.

6. Conclusion

Alumina-spinel materials are successfully used as reliable and cost effective linings for steel ladles. Applying a total cost of ownership approach, they

provide advantages such as reduced lining thickness enabling higher ladle capacity, a positive impact on steel quality, and reduction of energy losses. The growing demand for high quality automotive steel in India will further drive the use of alumina-spinel ladle linings.

Recent market changes regarding availability and pricing of magnesia material from China are triggering new considerations and projects to replace magnesia-carbon with alumina-spinel materials in steel ladles at steel works in different parts of the world. Monolithic steel ladle lining can probably be considered the most sophisticated and cost effective approach for alumina-spinel ladle lining. Fired alumina-spinel bricks are a proven alternative when a steel plant does not want to make the big technology change towards monolithic lining.

References

- 1) www.50years-worldsteel.org.
- 2) Buhr A et al., RWF 8 (2016) [1], 57-63.
- 3) Kriechbaum GW et al., 35. Int. Colloq. Refractories, Aachen/ Germany, 1992.
- 4) Schnabel M, et al., RWF 2 (2010) [2], 87-93.
- 5) Braulio M et al., Ceramics International 37 (2011) [6], 1705-1724.
- 6) Buhr A., CN-Refractories 6 (1999) [3], 19-30.
- 7) Exenberger R., voestalpine Stahl GmbH Linz, Steel Ladle Lining (SSL), Steel Academy, Hannover/Germany, 2012 and Mönchengladbach/Germany, 2016.
- 8) Vatanen J. SSAB Europe Oy, SSL, Steel Academy, Mönchengladbach/ Germany, 2016.
- 9) Breithaupt M., Badische Stahlwerke, SSL, Steel Academy, Hannover/Germany, 2012.
- 10) Lamm R, Refractory Technology, Cologne/ Germany, 22-25 April 2018.
- 11) Franken MC et al, UNITECR'01, Cancun/Mexico, Vol. I, p. 128-138.
- 12) Peekel M., Tata Steel Ijmuiden, SSL, Steel Academy, Mönchengladbach/ Germany, 2016.
- 13) Chatterjee S, Buhr A, Pal A, Singh B., UNITECR'17, Santiago/Chile, paper no.76.
- 14) Siebring R, Buhr A. Economics in refractory usage, Refractory Technology, Steel Academy, Cologne/Germany, 22-25 April 2018.
- 15) www.steeluniversity.org
- 16) Refractory committee VDEh., April 2014.
- 17) www.minerals.usgs.gov/minerals/
- 18) O'Driscoll M., IREFCON 2018, Delhi/India.